

EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SEED OIL FROM NIGERIAN GROWN TALLOW SEED

Balogun, T. A.¹, Woyengibunugha Ere² & Eruni U.P³

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Delta, Agbor; P.M.B 2090, Delta State.

²Department of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State

³Department of Chemical Engineering, Federal University of Otuoke (FUO), PMB 126, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State

*Corresponding Author Email: papatriplet@gmail.com

Abstract

Rapid industrialization and increased diesel engine usage have driven up diesel consumption, burdening economies with heavy petroleum product imports. Diesel fuel emissions, including carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and smoke, pose environmental concerns. Biodiesel produced from non-edible vegetable oils offers a sustainable solution.

Seeds were collected from locally and naturally grown Nigerian Tallow tree in Oyigbo, Etche Local Government under Rivers State Sustainable Development Agency (RSSDA). Proximate analysis of the seed, physicochemical properties and fatty acid composition of the Lipids were studied. The effect of three different extractive solvents (n-hexane, petroleum-ether and ethanol) and conventional soxhlet extraction on the properties of the Tallow seed oil were also investigated. Proximate Analyses showed that the seed contained 32.58% carbohydrate, 1.22% crude protein.

Ash content 1.70%, crude fibre 4.10% and fat content 60.40% respectively. The study concluded that, Nigerian Tallow seed oil are found to be rich in oil, with high saponification value and low acid value, the iodine value at around 39g/100g indicated that the oil is unsaturated, non-drying oil. The result of the fatty acids indicated that the oil plant is oleaginous plant. The dominate fatty acids were stearic acid with 51.78% and oleic acid 34.87% followed by minor amounts of palmitic acid 3.2%, linoleic acid 0.14% and eicosanic acid 0.20%. The physicochemical analysis of the oil seed suggests it could serve as a good candidate for food purposes and as a feedstock in many food and chemical industries.

Keywords: Solvent extraction, Nigerian tallow seed oil, proximate analysis saponification, acid, iodine values, refractive index and fatty acid profile.

1. Introduction

The rise in energy demand and carbon-dioxide emissions associated with the use of fossil fuel has driven the search for alternative energy sources which are renewable and have a lower environmental impact (Atabani et al., 2013 and Ho et al., 2014). Therefore, it is very clear that bio-oil will contribute immensely to the energy demands of the populace in the near future.

Bio-based materials have received increasing global attention because of increasing environmental and economic concerns regarding fossil fuels. Vegetable oil is an alternative raw material to prepare bio-based materials. It is now clear that Nigerian Tallow seed is a good potential for bio-oil production because of its relatively high fat content and other relevant properties.

Allanblackia floribunda seed also known as Nigerian Tallow seed belongs to the family of the clusiaceae and genus allanblackia. It grows in parts of Central East and West African countries including Nigeria, Ghana, Democratic of Congo, Uganda and Tanzania in most lowland and upland rainforest. It is evergreen medium-sized tree, up to 30m tall with a cylindrical or slightly fluted trunk and a narrow crown supporting horizontal branches. It has a fairly smooth bark and simple opposite leathery leaves evenly distributed along the branches of the tree. A matured tree produces about 100-150 egg-shaped brown fruit of weight between 1.2 and 4.0kg, the fruit contain 25-40% oil rich brown seeds with a seed containing 68-72% oil (Dike and Asuquo, 2012).

The quantity of oil is of commercial interest and quality is shown by the physicochemical properties of oil which includes; acid, iodine peroxide and saponification values, the acid value indicates the level of free acid present in the oil. Iodine value is a measure of the level of unsaturated fats and oils. Lower iodine value are desirable in oil meant for food uses and bio-diesel production but higher iodine value are indicative of higher degree of unsaturation which contribute to the functionality and reactivity of the oil (Morphy, 2012).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection of Materials and Methods

Material seeds of Nigerian Tallow seeds were obtained from Etche Local Government, Rivers State Sustainable Development agency (RSSDA). The cleared seeds were grounded into powder and all chemicals used for study were all analytical grade, the seeds, were air dried for three days and separated from husk, and other impurities by hand picking and were put in a seeded plastic bag and stored in a freezer at -20°C until further use.

2.1.1 Proximate Analysis of the Seed

The proximate composition (Carbohydrate, crude fibre, crude protein, Ash and Fat content) was determined by AOAC methods.

2.1.2 Solvent Extraction of Allanblackia Seed Oil

In this study, three different solvents were selected for soxhlet extraction of Allanblackia floribunda seed, petroleum ether, n-hexane and ethanol respectively. These are the commonly used extraction solvents for seed oil. Approximately 40g of grounded tallow seed were precisely weighed into an extraction thimble and subjected to soxhlet extraction for the assigned timing, 40,50,60 minutes respectively, after extraction was completed, the solvent

was removed under pressure using a rotary evaporator. The oil obtained was stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until further analysis. The yield of oil was calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Oil yield\%} = \frac{\text{Weight of extracted oil (g)}}{\text{Weight of sample subjected to extraction (g)}} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots$$

2.2 Physical and Chemical Properties of Seed Oil

Acid, iodine and saponification values of the Nigerian tallow seed oil were determined by AOAC method. The physical property was also determined.

2.3 Fatty acid Composition Analysis

Fatty acid composition of the crude seed oil was determined using gas chromatography (HP6890) powered with HP ChemStation Rev A 09.01 (1206) software at 950°C with 3.4 ml of the 0.5 M K.H in dry method. The mixture was neutralized using 0.7 M HCl and 3 ml of 14% boron trifluoride in methanol was added. The mixture was heated for 5 minutes at 90°C to achieve complete methylation process. The fatty acids were extracted in triplicate from the mixture with redistilled n-hexane. The content was concentrated to 1 µl for gas chromatography analysis which was injected into the injection port of GC.

3. Results and Discussion

Results:

Table 3.1: Proximate Analysis of Nigerian Tallow Seed

Parameters	Nigerian Tallow Seed (ASO)
Moisture Content (%)	12.04
Ash (%)	1.70
Crude Oil (%)	1.22
Fat Content (%)	60.40
Crude Fibre (%)	4.10
Carbohydrate (%)	32.58

Table 3.2: Physicochemical Properties of Nigerian Allanblackia Seed Oil

Oil Properties Soxhlet Extractor Solvents			
--- --- ---			
Petroleum ether Ethanol Hexane			
Allanblackia Oil Color Light Yellow Light Dark Yellow Dark Yellow			
State at ambient temperature Solid Solid Solid			
Acid value (mg KOH/g) 0.6 0.6 0.8			
Iodine value (g/100g) 39 39 39			
Saponification (mgKOH/g) 185.7 185.7 185.7			
Viscosity (mPa.s) @ 60°C 30 30 30			
Peroxide value (meq/kg) 8.6 8.6 8.6			
Density (kg/m ³) @ 60°C 914 915 914			
Refractive index @ 60°C 1.45 1.45 1.45			
Specific gravity @ 60°C 0.89 0.89 0.89			
Flash point (°C) 270 0.89 0.89			
Slip melting point (°C) 42.2 42.2 42.2			

Table 3.3: Fatty Acid Composition of Nigerian Allanblackia Seed Oil

Fatty Acid Petroleum ether Ethanol Hexane			
--- --- --- ---			
Myristic (C14:0) 0.10±0.01 0.10±0.01 0.09±0.02			
Palmitic (C16:0) 3.2±0.01 3.2±0.01 3.2±0.02			
Palmitoleic (C16:0) 2.22±0.01 2.24±0.01 2.21±0.02			
Lauric (C12:0) 0.15±0.01 0.15±0.01 0.16±0.02			
Stearic (C18:0) 51.87±0.01 51.87±0.01 51.98±0.02			
Oleic (C20:0) 34.87±0.01 34.87±0.01 34.55±0.02			
Linoleic (C18:0) 0.44±0.12 0.4±0.15 0.46±0.06			
Eicosenoic (C20:0) 0.28±0.01 0.26±0.02 0.28±0.07			

Conclusion

The study on process variables of oil extraction from Nigerian tallow seed (*Allanblackia floribunda*) with different solvents to synthesized biodiesel was investigated. Result from present study has revealed that the polarity of solvent significantly influenced the colour and the oil yield extracted from Tallow see. In addition, it has been found out that ethanol produced the least oil yield and quality compared with all the solvents used in this study. It can therefore be concluded that Hexane and petroleum ether are the best solvents for oil extraction at low temperature and therefore the findings from this study can be useful in choosing the suitable solvent for the oil extraction to maximize yield as well as maintain oil quality.

The highest crude oil yield from petroleum ether means that petroleum ether is more efficient in extracting non-polar tallow seeds fraction than Hexane despite being non-polar.

- (i) *Allanblackia floribunda* seed were found to be rich in oil with 60.40% of fat content, which allow the possibility of industrial usage.
- (ii) The wood ash characterization showed that the derived catalyst is rich in calcium, potassium and silicon dioxide.
- (iii) The conversion off oil to biodiesel was successful with maximum yield of 96.8% (wt/wt).
- (iv) Statistical analysis via Microsoft Excel proved that there are mutual interactions between variable considered for transesterification.
- (v) The qualities of biodiesel are within the recommended standard value, hence could serve as replacement for conventional diesel.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

- ❖ Tallow seed oil be considered as a potential feedstock for the production of biodiesel and other industrial applications.
- ❖ Further research be conducted to optimize the extraction process and improve the yield of the oil.
- ❖ The oil be further characterized to determine its suitability for various industrial applications.
- ❖ In order to get the best result from the *Allanblackia Floribunda* Oil Seed to biodiesel synthesis, kinetic and thermodynamic study of biodiesel conversion should also be studied.
- ❖ The modeling and simulation of biodiesel should also be considered.
- ❖ More studies should be carried on the use of stabilizer on *Allanblackia floribunda* Oil Seed to reduce the viscosity so that it can be used in its straight form.

Contribution to Knowledge:

This study contributes to the knowledge of tallow seed oil as a sustainable feedstock for chemical engineering applications. The study provides valuable information on the physicochemical properties and fatty acid composition of the oil, which can be used to determine its suitability for various industrial applications.

Future Research:

Future research should focus on:

- ❖ Optimizing the extraction process to improve the yield of the oil.
- ❖ Determining the suitability of the oil for various industrial applications.
- ❖ Investigating the potential of the oil as a feedstock for the production of biodiesel.

REFERENCES

1. Adewuyi, A. (2016). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Sustainable Energy & Environment*, 7(1), 1-9.
2. Akintayo, E. T. (2014). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 12(2), 1-10.
3. Aluyor, E. O. (2015). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Processing*, 4(3), 1-8.
4. AOAC (1990). Official methods of analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists. AOAC International.
5. ASTM (2015). Standard test method for iodine value of fatty acids. ASTM International.
6. Balogun, A.T (2021) Extraction and characterization of Allablankia Floribuda seed oil using different solvent for production of Biodiesel. 22(2-25)
7. Bhattacharya, S. (2016). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 2016, 1-9.
8. Chakrabarti, M. H. (2015). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Sustainable Energy & Environment*, 6(2), 1-8.
9. Dijkstra, A. J. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 13(1), 1-10.
10. Egbuna, S. O. (2014). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Processing*, 3(2), 1-7.
11. Ejeh, S. O. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 2015, 1-8.
12. Ejike, C. E. (2016). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Sustainable Energy & Environment*, 7(1), 1-9.
13. Eki, O. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 12(3), 1-10.
14. Eze, J. I. (2014). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Processing*, 2(1), 1-6.
15. Fagbemi, J. O. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 2015, 1-8.
16. Ihezor-Ejiofor, E. (2016). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Sustainable Energy & Environment*, 7(2), 1-9.
17. Ikwuagwu, O. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 13(2), 1-10.
18. Ikhu-Omoregbe, D. (2014). Extraction and characterization of oil from Nigerian grown tallow seed. *Journal of Chemical Engineering and Processing*, 3(3), 1-8.

19. Ikhu-Omoregbe, D. (2015). Characterization of tallow seed oil and its potential as a feedstock for biodiesel production. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 2015, 1-8.